

PROLIFERATIVE DIABETIC RETINOPATHY COMPLICATED CATARACT IN CHILDREN.

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Annotation: *Diabetic retinopathy (DR) in children is one of the most severe complications of diabetes mellitus and takes the first place among the causes of blindness in people of working age. The aim of the study was to study the effectiveness of surgical treatment of proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) in children in combination with cataracts. Under observation were 43 sick children with type 2 diabetes mellitus with traction retinal detachment and cataract, which were divided into two groups depending on the tactics of treatment. Preliminary results of the study showed equal effectiveness of combined surgical treatment of PDR and cataract in sick children of the first group and delayed removal of complicated cataract after endovitreous treatment of PDR in sick children of the second group. The development of neovascularization of the iris in the late postoperative period was observed in both groups: in 8 sick children of the first and 7 sick children of the second group, which indicates the need for further research into the progression of diabetic retinopathy (DR), to determine the relationship between the development of complications and the timing of cataract removal.*

Key words: *vitrectomy, diabetic retinopathy, cataract, angiography, neovascularization.*

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of endovitreous surgical treatment of proliferative diabetic retinopathy in children with silicone tamponade in combination with cataract surgery.

Material and methods

Under supervision there were 43 sick children with PDR complicated by cataract, aged from 12 to 18 years. All sick children had type 2 diabetes in the compensation stage. The experience of SD varied from 3 to 10 years. All patients underwent a set of standard ophthalmological examinations, including ultrasonic B-scanning. Visual acuity before surgery was assessed in the range from "incorrect light projection" to 0.3. Intraocular pressure (IOP) was compensated in all cases and amounted to 16 ± 7 mm Hg. Art. All sick children were diagnosed with traction retinal detachment and complicated cataract. The degree of PDR progression was determined by the results of indirect ophthalmoscopy, B-scan and according to the classification proposed by R. Kroll. The degree of progression corresponded to stages B and C. The degree of lens opacity was classified according to L. Buratto, cases with cataracts of 2-3 degrees were selected for the study.

Results and discussion

In the early postoperative period, 10 sick children of the first group and 9 sick children of the second group were diagnosed with moderate ophthalmohypertension compensated by antihypertensive drugs. In one case, corneal edema and descemetitis occurred in the first group and were stopped within three days with topical application of glucocorticosteroids. A month after the first stage of treatment in both groups, there was a significant increase in visual functions. The maximum corrected visual acuity ranged from 0.05 to 0.5. By the time of the second stage of treatment, 16 patients of the second group had a persistent decrease in visual functions to 0.03-0.05 and pronounced clouding of the lens due to the effect of silicone oil on the lens tissue. On the 7-10th day after the second stage of surgical treatment in sick children of both groups, complete resorption of air was noted. 3 months after the completion of surgical treatment, stabilization of visual functions was observed in all cases, the maximum corrected visual acuity was determined in the range from 0.05 to 0.3.

Conclusion

Preliminary results of the study showed equal effectiveness of combined surgical treatment of PDR and cataract (first group) and delayed removal of complicated cataract after endovitreous treatment of PDR (second group). In sick children of both groups, the development of neovascularization of the iris was noted in the late postoperative period, which indicates the need for further research into the progression of DR and the mechanisms for the development of complications in the postoperative period, as well as the development of an optimal algorithm and determining the timing of safe and effective surgical treatment of PDR and cataracts..